

Supplementary material for the manuscript:

Pregnancy exposure to perfluoroalkyl substances, prolactin concentrations and breastfeeding in the Odense Child Cohort

Supplementary table 1: Cox regression. Hazard Ratios and 95% confidence intervals for terminating breastfeeding with each doubling in maternal serum-PFAS concentrations. Excluding women who never initiated breastfeeding or breastfed less than one week.

	Total breastfeeding HR (95% CI)	Exclusive breastfeeding HR (95% CI)
Crude	n=1118	n=1061
PFHxS	1.06 (0.99, 1.13)	0.95 (0.89, 1.01)
PFOS	1.25 (1.15, 1.36)	1.02 (0.94, 1.10)
PFOA	1.23 (1.14, 1.31)	1.11 (1.04, 1.19)
PFNA	1.23 (1.13, 1.34)	0.99 (0.91, 1.08)
PFDA	1.06 (0.98, 1.14)	0.99 (0.92, 1.07)
∑PFAS	1.31 (1.19, 1.43)	1.04 (0.96, 1.14)
Reduced^a	n=816	n=772
PFHxS	1.07 (1.00, 1.15)	0.94 (0.88, 1.01)
PFOS	1.25 (1.14, 1.38)	0.99 (0.90, 1.09)
PFOA	1.19 (1.10, 1.30)	1.08 (1.00, 1.18)
PFNA	1.21 (1.09, 1.33)	0.94 (0.85, 1.04)
PFDA	1.02 (0.93, 1.11)	0.98 (0.90, 1.07)
∑PFAS	1.29 (1.17, 1.44)	1.01 (0.91, 1.12)
Adjusted^b	n=816	n=772
PFHxS	1.06 (0.98, 1.16)	0.92 (0.86, 0.99)
PFOS	1.18 (1.06, 1.32)	0.96 (0.87, 1.07)
PFOA	1.15 (1.04, 1.28)	1.03 (0.93, 1.13)
PFNA	1.17 (1.05, 1.30)	0.90 (0.81, 1.01)
PFDA	0.99 (0.91, 1.09)	0.97 (0.88, 1.06)
∑PFAS	1.22 (1.08, 1.39)	0.95 (0.85, 1.07)
Censored^{b, c}	n=816	n=772
PFHxS	1.05 (0.96, 1.15)	0.91 (0.84, 0.98)
PFOS	1.18 (1.05, 1.33)	0.94 (0.84, 1.05)
PFOA	1.17 (1.05, 1.31)	1.02 (0.92, 1.13)
PFNA	1.18 (1.05, 1.32)	0.89 (0.79, 0.99)
PFDA	1.03 (0.94, 1.13)	0.98 (0.89, 1.07)
∑PFAS	1.24 (1.08, 1.41)	0.93 (0.83, 1.05)

^a Excluding women with missing information about parity, education, BMI, smoking, national origin, expectations of giving formula, duration of previous breastfeeding, or previous inadequate lactation

^b Adjusted for education, BMI, national origin, and expectations of giving formula. Stratified by parity, smoking, duration of previous breastfeeding, and previous inadequate lactation

^c Women for whom reasons for early termination of breastfeeding was either given as not related to insufficient lactation or not given in the health visitor's report were censored when terminating breastfeeding

Supplementary table 2: Cox regression. Hazard Ratios and 95% confidence intervals for terminating breastfeeding with each doubling in maternal serum-PFAS concentrations among primiparous and multiparous women

	Total breastfeeding (weeks) ^{a,b}			Exclusive breastfeeding (weeks) ^{a,b}		
	Primiparous HR (95% CI)	Multiparous HR (95% CI)	p ^c	Primiparous HR (95% CI)	Multiparous HR (95% CI)	p ^c
	n=507	n=336		n=554	n=373	
PFHxS	1.04 (0.93, 1.16)	1.08 (0.94, 1.23)	0.719	0.94 (0.85, 1.03)	0.90 (0.83, 0.98)	0.581
PFOS	1.15 (1.00, 1.33)	1.19 (0.98, 1.45)	0.783	0.95 (0.84, 1.08)	0.92 (0.80, 1.05)	0.704
PFOA	1.19 (1.04, 1.37)	1.12 (0.96, 1.32)	0.585	0.98 (0.87, 1.12)	1.08 (0.93, 1.24)	0.351
PFNA	1.18 (1.02, 1.36)	1.17 (0.98, 1.40)	0.934	0.89 (0.78, 1.02)	0.96 (0.82, 1.12)	0.480
PFDA	1.03 (0.91, 1.16)	1.05 (0.91, 1.22)	0.786	0.97 (0.86, 1.09)	0.98 (0.86, 1.12)	0.874
Σ PFAS	1.21 (1.03, 1.43)	1.23 (1.00, 1.52)	0.919	0.94 (0.81, 1.09)	0.94 (0.81, 1.09)	0.995

^a Adjusted for education, BMI, national origin, expectations of giving formula, duration of previous breastfeeding, and previous inadequate lactation. Stratified by smoking

^b Women for whom reasons for early termination of breastfeeding was either given as not related to insufficient lactation or not given in the health visitor's report were censored when terminating breastfeeding

^c p-value for interaction between parity and PFAS

Supplementary table 3: Linear regression. Differences in pregnancy prolactin concentrations with a doubling in maternal serum-PFAS concentrations among women with and without risk factors for Gestational Diabetes Mellitus (GDM)

Prolactin GA week 10^a			
	No GDM risk	GDM risk	
	% difference (95% CI)	% difference (95% CI)	p^b
	n=228	n=230	
PFHxS	-6.2 (-12.0, 0.1)	0.9 (-6.7, 9.2)	0.141
PFOS	-0.4 (-11.5, 12.2)	4.1 (-6.5, 15.8)	0.583
PFOA	-2.9 (-11.0, 5.9)	3.6 (-4.5, 12.4)	0.256
PFNA	0.8 (-9.2, 12.0)	5.8 (-4.5, 17.2)	0.514
PFDA	-1.3 (-9.7, 7.8)	16.3 (5.8, 27.8)	0.012
ΣPFAS	-1.7 (-13.2, 11.3)	6.9 (-4.2, 19.4)	0.303
Prolactin GA week 28^a			
	No GDM risk	GDM risk	
	% difference (95% CI)	% difference (95% CI)	p^b
	n=227	n=232	
PFHxS	1.4 (-2.6, 5.6)	-1.3 (-6.2, 4.0)	0.423
PFOS	6.6 (-1.5, 15.4)	1.1 (-6.4, 9.2)	0.343
PFOA	3.7 (-2.4, 10.1)	0.3 (-5.1, 6.0)	0.417
PFNA	6.9 (-0.3, 14.6)	2.4 (-4.8, 10.1)	0.404
PFDA	3.9 (-2.9, 11.1)	8.0 (1.3, 15.3)	0.416
ΣPFAS	7.7 (-0.8, 17.0)	1.9 (-6.0, 10.6)	0.348
Prolactin change from GA week 10 to 28 (mIU/L)^a			
	No GDM risk	GDM risk	
	Difference (95% CI)	Difference (95% CI)	p^b
	n=227	n=230	
PFHxS	109.9 (-97.1, 316.9)	-36.2 (-275.0, 202.5)	0.354
PFOS	342.0 (-29.0, 713.1)	43.6 (-301.9, 389.1)	0.240
PFOA	165.2 (-119.6, 450.1)	-3.7 (-254.6, 247.2)	0.359
PFNA	288.2 (-53.9, 630.3)	98.6 (-299.2, 496.4)	0.477
PFDA	208.8 (-116.1, 533.7)	192.9 (-128.9, 514.8)	0.946
ΣPFAS	380.5 (-11.3, 772.4)	56.7 (-318.1, 431.5)	0.228

^a Adjusted for timing of prolactin measurements, parity, BMI, and smoking

^b p-value for interaction between PFAS and risk of GDM

Supplementary table 4: Cox regression. Hazard Ratios and 95% confidence intervals for terminating breastfeeding with each doubling in maternal serum-PFAS concentrations – additional adjustment for prolactin

	Total breastfeeding	Exclusive breastfeeding
	HR (95% CI)	HR (95% CI)
Adjusted ^{a,b,c}	n=701	n=775
PFHxS	1.05 (0.96, 1.16)	0.91 (0.85, 0.98)
PFOS	1.23 (1.08, 1.42)	0.93 (0.82, 1.04)
PFOA	1.18 (1.05, 1.33)	1.04 (0.94, 1.15)
PFNA	1.18 (1.05, 1.33)	0.91 (0.81, 1.02)
PFDA	1.02 (0.92, 1.14)	0.98 (0.88, 1.09)
∑PFAS	1.28 (1.10, 1.49)	0.94 (0.83, 1.07)
Additional adjustment for prolactin ^{a,b,d}	n=701	n=775
PFHxS	1.05 (0.96, 1.15)	0.91 (0.84, 0.97)
PFOS	1.25 (1.09, 1.44)	0.92 (0.82, 1.04)
PFOA	1.19 (1.05, 1.34)	1.05 (0.94, 1.16)
PFNA	1.20 (1.06, 1.35)	0.91 (0.81, 1.02)
PFDA	1.03 (0.93, 1.15)	0.97 (0.88, 1.08)
∑PFAS	1.30 (1.12, 1.51)	0.94 (0.83, 1.07)

^a Adjusted for education, BMI, national origin, and expectations of giving formula. Stratified by parity, smoking, duration of previous breastfeeding, and previous inadequate lactation

^b Women for whom reasons for early termination of breastfeeding was either given as not related to insufficient lactation or not given in the health visitor's report were censored

^c Analysis performed only among mothers who had prolactin measured at GA week 10 and 28

^d Adjusted for GA week 10 and 28 prolactin concentrations (log10 transformed) and timing of prolactin measurement